

ALGORITHM OF APPLYING THE INTERVAL METHOD

Kydyraliev S.,*Professor of the American University of Central Asia***Urdaletova A.,***Professor of the Kyrgyz-Turkish University "Manas"***Burova E.,***Assistant Professor of the American University of Central Asia***Japarova S.***Associate Professor of the K.Tynystanov Issyk-Kul State University***Abstract**

About 400 years ago, analytical geometry was born, and it "officially" used algebraic methods to solve geometric problems. It helped make a huge leap forward in the development of mathematics. Outstanding mathematicians immediately appreciated the effectiveness of analytical geometry methods. Among those who made a significant contribution to its development are Newton, Clairaut, Euler, Lagrange, and many others.

A less noticeable, but very effective step in teaching mathematics was the introduction of the Interval Method. Perhaps this is due to the very high naturalness of this method. Full use of the idea of continuity of a function allows us to practically do away with the separate consideration of the topic of Inequalities in the school mathematics course, reducing the process of solving inequalities by 99% to solving equations.

In our work, the Interval Method is illustrated by examples.

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1. To begin our discussion of the Interval Method, let's consider the function

$$y = \frac{(2x+1)(x-1)(x-4)}{(x-2)}$$

Its graph has a discontinuity at $x = 2$ and intersects the OX axis at $x = 0.5$, $x = 1$, $x = 4$. In other words, the function is not defined at $x = 2$, and the equation $y = 0$ has roots

$$x = 0.5, x = 1, x = 4.$$

Accordingly, these points uniquely determine solutions to inequalities of the type $y > 0$ or $y \leq 0$. Thus, in the case of $y > 0$, the solution $(-\infty; -0.5) \cup (1; 2) \cup (4; +\infty)$, and in the case of $y \leq 0$, the solution

$$[-0.5; 1] \cup (2; 4].$$

This example illustrates the main provisions of the Interval Method, which is the subject of this paper.

2. So, let us formulate an algorithm for solving inequalities using the Interval Method:

I. Determine the domain of the inequality;

II. Divide the domain of the inequality into subdomains by points that are the roots of the

equation that results if the inequality sign is replaced by the equality;

III. Check the inequality at one point in each subdomain;

IV. Write the solution to the inequality as a union of the subdomains in which the required inequality is satisfied.

Next, we illustrate the algorithm with examples.

3. Solve the inequality $2 + 5x > 10 + 7x$.

I. The domain of the inequality: $(-\infty; +\infty)$;

II. The root of the equation $2 + 5x = 10 + 7x < \Rightarrow -2x = 8 \Leftrightarrow x = -4$ is the number -4 . It divides the domain into subdomains $(-\infty; -4)$ and $(-4; +\infty)$;

III. At point $x = -10$, which belongs to $(-\infty; -4)$, the true inequality $2 + 5(-10) > 10 + 7(-10) \Leftrightarrow -48 > -60$ holds. At point $x = 0$, which belongs to $(-4; +\infty)$, the original inequality: $2 + 5 \cdot 0 > 10 + 7 \cdot 0 \Leftrightarrow 2 > 10$ does not hold;

IV. Therefore, **answer:** $(-\infty; -4)$.

Of course, the given solution is practically no different from the generally accepted one:

1. Move the variables to one (left) side, and the numbers to the other (right) side of the inequality: $5x - 7x > 10 - 2$.

We get: $-2x > 8$;

1. Divide both parts by -2 : $-2x/(-2) > 8/(-2)$. In this case, we must not forget to change the inequality sign to the opposite, since -2 is a negative number: $x < -4$.

Answer: $x < -4$ or, in equivalent form, $x \in (-\infty; -4)$.

4. Solve the inequality $5x^2 - 12x + 4 \leq 0$.

I. Domain of the inequality: $(-\infty; +\infty)$;

II. The roots of the equation $5x^2 - 12x + 4 = 0$ are the numbers 0.4; 2. They divide the domain into subdomains $(-\infty; 0.4)$, $(0.4; 2)$ and $(2; +\infty)$;

III. At point $x = 0$, which belongs to $(-\infty; 0.4)$, the inequality:

$5 \cdot 0^2 - 12 \cdot 0 + 4 \leq 0$ is false. At point $x = 1$, which belongs to $(0.4; 2)$, the inequality: $5 \cdot 1^2 - 12 \cdot 1 + 4 = -3 \leq 0$ is true. At point $x = 10$, which belongs to $(2; +\infty)$, the inequality: $5 \cdot 10^2 - 12 \cdot 10 + 4 \leq 0$ is false.

IV. **Answer:** $[0.4; 2]$.

5. Solve the inequality $\frac{x-1}{x^2-5x} > \frac{2}{2x+3}$.

6. Solve the inequality $0.25^x + 0.5^x > 2$.

I. Domain: $(-\infty; -1.5) \cup (-1.5; 0) \cup (0; 5) \cup (5; +\infty)$;

II. The root of the equation $\frac{x-1}{x^2-5x} = \frac{2}{2x+3} \Rightarrow (x-1)(2x+3) = 2(x^2-5x) \Rightarrow 2x^2 + x - 3 = 2x^2 - 10x \Rightarrow 11x = 3 \Rightarrow x = 3/11$ is the number $3/11$. It divides the domain into subdomains

$(-\infty; -1.5)$, $(-1.5; 0)$, $(0; \frac{3}{11})$, $(\frac{3}{11}; 5)$, $(5; +\infty)$;

III. At the point $x = -10$, which belongs to $(-\infty; -1.5)$, the following inequality holds: $\frac{(-10)-1}{(-10)^2-5(-10)} > \frac{2}{2(-10)+3} \Leftrightarrow \frac{-11}{150} > \frac{2}{-17} \Leftrightarrow \frac{-22}{300} > \frac{-22}{187}$.

At the point $x = -1$, which belongs to $(-1.5; 0)$, the inequality: $\frac{(-1)-1}{(-1)^2-5(-1)} > \frac{2}{2(-1)+3} \Leftrightarrow \frac{-2}{6} > \frac{2}{1}$ is false.

At the point $x = 0.1$, which belongs to $(0; \frac{3}{11})$ the inequality:

$\frac{0.1-1}{0.1^2-5 \cdot 0.1} > \frac{2}{2 \cdot 0.1+3} \Leftrightarrow \frac{-0.9}{-0.49} > \frac{2}{3.2} \Leftrightarrow \frac{90}{49} > \frac{90}{144}$ is true.

At point $x = 1$, which belongs to $(\frac{3}{11}; 5)$, the inequality:

$\frac{1-1}{1^2-5 \cdot 1} > \frac{2}{2 \cdot 1+3} \Leftrightarrow 0 > \frac{2}{5}$, is false.

At point $x = 10$, which belongs to $(5; +\infty)$, the true inequality holds: $\frac{10-1}{10^2-5 \cdot 10} > \frac{2}{2 \cdot 10+3} \Leftrightarrow \frac{9}{50} > \frac{6}{69}$.

IV. **Answer:** $(-\infty; -1.5) \cup (0; \frac{3}{11}) \cup (5; +\infty)$.

To illustrate the example, we use the graph of the function $y = \frac{x-1}{x^2-5x} - \frac{2}{2x+3}$.

I. Domain: $(-\infty; +\infty)$;

II. To solve the equation $0.25^x + 0.5^x = 2$, we use the change of variable $y = 0.5^x$. Then, we get the equation $y^2 + y - 2 = 0$ with roots $y_1 = 1$; $y_2 = -2$. Returning to the original variables, we get: $y = -2 = > 0.5^x = -2$ has no roots; $y = 1 \Rightarrow 0.5^x = 1 \Rightarrow x = 0$. Thus, it turned out that the equation $0.25^x + 0.5^x = 2$ has a single root $x = 0$. It divides the domain into subdomains $(-\infty; 0)$, $(0; +\infty)$;

III. At the point $x = -1$, which belongs to $(-\infty; 0)$, the following inequality holds: $0.25^{-1} + 0.5^{-1} > 2 \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{-1} + \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{-1} > 2 \Leftrightarrow 4 + 2 > 2$.

At point $x = 1$, which belongs to $(0; +\infty)$, the inequality:

$$0.25^1 + 0.5^1 > 2 \Leftrightarrow 0.75 > 2 \text{ is false.}$$

IV. Answer: $(-\infty; 0)$.

7. In some cases, to determine the domain of an inequality, you have to solve the inequality. You shouldn't be too shy about this: you just need to go through the appropriate algorithm for solving the inequality.

Solve the inequality $\log_{x-2}(2x - 3) > \log_{x-2}(30 - 6x)$.

I. The domain of the logarithmic function assumes that the base must be positive and not equal to 1: $x - 2 > 0$; $x - 2 \neq 1 \Leftrightarrow x > 2$; $x \neq 3$. The exponent must also be positive: that is, $2x - 3 > 0 \Leftrightarrow x > 1.5$ and $30 - 6x > 0 \Leftrightarrow x < 5$. Taking the intersection of all these domains, we obtain that the

8. Sometimes, in order to answer a question, it is not necessary to solve the corresponding equation.

domain of the the inequality $\log_{x-2}(2x - 3) > \log_{x-2}(30 - 6x)$ is satisfied by the set $(2; 3) \cup (3; 5)$;

II. Since the bases of the logarithms are the same, the equation

$\log_{x-2}(2x - 3) = \log_{x-2}(30 - 6x)$ must have the same exponents:

$$2x - 3 = 30 - 6x \Leftrightarrow 8x = 33 \Leftrightarrow x = 4.125. \text{ Thus, the root of the equation}$$

$\log_{x-2}(2x - 3) = \log_{x-2}(30 - 6x)$ divides the domain of definition of the original inequality into subdomains $(2; 3)$, $(3; 4.125)$, $(4.125; 5)$;

III. At the point $x = 2.5$, which belongs to $(2; 3)$, the following inequality holds: $\log_{2.5-2}(2 \cdot 2.5 - 3) > \log_{2.5-2}(30 - 6 \cdot 2.5) \Leftrightarrow \log_{0.5}2 > \log_{0.5}15$, because the logarithm to the base 0.5 is a decreasing function.

At the point $x = 4$, which belongs to $(3; 4.125)$, the inequality:

$$\log_{4-2}(2 \cdot 4 - 3) > \log_{4-2}(30 - 6 \cdot 4) \Leftrightarrow \log_25 > \log_26 \text{ is false, because the logarithm with a base greater than one is an increasing function.}$$

At the point $x = 4.5$, which belongs to $(4.125; 5)$, the inequality:

$$\log_{4.5-2}(2 \cdot 4.5 - 3) > \log_{4.5-2}(30 - 6 \cdot 4.5) \Leftrightarrow \log_{2.5}6 > \log_{2.5}3 \text{ is true.}$$

IV. Answer: $(2; 3) \cup (4.125; 5)$.

To illustrate the example, we will use the graph of the function

$$y = \log_{x-2}(2x - 3) - \log_{x-2}(30 - 6x):$$

Find the sum of integer solutions to the inequality $\sqrt{2+x-x^2} > 2x^2 - 3x - 1$.

I. The expression under the root must be non-negative: $2+x-x^2 \geq 0$. Since the equation $2+x-x^2 = 0$ has roots 2; -1, and at the point $x = 0$ the expression $2+x-x^2$ is positive, the domain of the inequality is $[-1; 2]$.

Of course, you can try to solve the equation, but what for? The domain contains only 4 integer values. Therefore, it is enough to check them directly. So, if;

$x = -1$, inequality $\sqrt{2+(-1)-(-1)^2} > 2(-1)^2 - 3(-1) - 1 \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{0} > 4$ is false;

$x = 0$, inequality $\sqrt{2+0-0^2} > 2 \cdot 0^2 - 3 \cdot 0 - 1 \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{2} > -1$ is true;

$x = 1$, inequality $\sqrt{2+1-1^2} > 2 \cdot 1^2 - 3 \cdot 1 - 1 \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{2} > -2$ is true;

$x = 2$, inequality $\sqrt{2+2-2^2} > 2 \cdot 2^2 - 3 \cdot 2 - 1 \Leftrightarrow \sqrt{0} > 1$ is false.

Answer: $0 + 1 = 1$.

9. The following inequality was proposed at the AUCA Olympiad in Mathematics for schoolchildren.

Solve the inequality: $(x^2 + 2x - 8)\log_2(9 - 0.8x) < 0$ and calculate the sum of all its integer roots.

Solution

Since the function $f(x) = x^2 + 2x - 8$ is defined for all x , the function

$g(x) = \log_2(9 - 0.8x)$ defines the domain of the inequality:

$9 - 0.8x > 0 \Leftrightarrow x < 11.25 \Leftrightarrow x \in (-\infty; 11.25)$.

Next, we find that the equation $x^2 + 2x - 8 = 0$ has roots 2; -4, and the equation $\log_2(9 - 0.8x) = 0$ has root 10, and we divide the domain of inequality into subdomains: $(-\infty; -4)$, $(-4; 2)$, $(2; 10)$, $(10; 11.25)$.

At point $x = -10$, which belongs to $(-\infty; -4)$, the inequality:

$((-10)^2 + 2(-10) - 8)\log_2(9 - 0.8(-10)) = 72\log_2 17 > 0$ is false.

At point $x = 0$, which belongs to $(-4; 2)$, the inequality:

$((0)^2 + 2(0) - 8)\log_2(9 - 0.8(0)) = -8\log_2 9 < 0$ is true.

At point $x = 5$, which belongs to $(2; 10)$, the inequality:

$(5^2 + 2 \cdot 5 - 8)\log_2(9 - 0.8 \cdot 5) = 27\log_2 5 > 0$ is false.

At point $x = 11$, which belongs to $(10; 11.25)$, the inequality:

$(11^2 + 2 \cdot 11 - 8)\log_2(9 - 0.8 \cdot 11) = 135\log_2 0.2 < 0$ is true.

Therefore, **answer:** $[(-3) + (-2) + (-1) + 0 + 1] + 11 = 6$.

Conclusion

In modern conditions, school education is in a state of total time deficit. Almost all subject teachers complain about the lack of "hours". At the same time, there are regular calls to introduce new subjects or new topics into the school education program. Therefore, the problem of improving teaching methods is very urgent. This applies even to such a classic subject as Math Mathematics.

Of course, knowledge of such rules as the need to change the inequality sign when multiplying/dividing it by a negative number, the need to take into account the decrease/increase of the exponential or logarithmic function depending on the base, is very important. But unfortunately, students make these mistakes again and again. Therefore, in our opinion, the widespread use of the Interval Method, which simplifies the process of solving inequalities and saves "deficit hours", is necessary for the process of teaching schoolchildren.

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